

Supplementary Materials for “Can Large Language Models Help Students Prove Software Correctness? An Experimental Study with Dafny”

Carolina Carreira¹, Álvaro Silva², Alexandre Abreu², and Alexandra Mendes²

¹ Carnegie Mellon University, USA, INESC-ID & IST, University of Lisbon, Portugal

² INESC TEC, Faculty of Engineering, University of Porto, Portugal

Survey

Consent

Our study involves a survey that aims to understand how students use ChatGPT when working on Dafny verification tasks. This survey is anonymous, no identifying information is collected. Insights from this survey will contribute to ongoing research about the ways automated tools can support (or hinder) the process of specifying, verifying, and reasoning about code in Dafny.

Procedures In this study, you’ll answer questions about your experience using ChatGPT for Dafny, including how often you rely on AI assistance, whether you trust its responses, and how helpful or unhelpful it may have been for specific verification subtasks. The expected duration of the survey is 60 minutes.

Participant Requirements Participation in this study is limited to individuals 18 years of age or older.

Risks The risks and discomfort associated with participation in this study are no greater than those ordinarily encountered in daily life or other online activities.

Compensation & Costs There may be no personal benefit from your participation in the study, but the knowledge received may be of value to humanity.

Voluntary Participation Your participation in this research is voluntary. You may discontinue participation at any time during the research activity.

Personal data and Confidentiality This survey is anonymous, no identifying information is collected.

Consent Statement I’m 18 years of age or older, I read and understand the information above, and I want to participate in this research and continue with the survey.

Yes

No

ChatGPT

1. **Step 1:** Open the ChatGPT Interface to use for any questions, or help with the Dafny exercise.
2. **Step 2:** Copy the session key into the question below.
This key is anonymous.

3. **Step 3:** Download the Exercise. The exercise is available in this Google Doc:
4. **Step 4:** Submit Your Code. Once you finish the exercise, upload your solution into the input box below the question. Please upload full code, even if incomplete.

Reminder: You can use the ChatGPT interface provided at LINK. *You only have 30 minutes to submit your response.*

Performance Rating: Based on the exercise you just completed, including both components, please rate your overall performance.

- Very poorly
- Poorly
- Neutral
- Well
- Very well

Confidence Level: How confident are you in the code you just submitted, considering both components of the exercise?

- Not at all confident
- Slightly confident
- Moderately confident
- Very confident
- Extremely confident

How much do you trust the accuracy of ChatGPT’s responses when working on the Dafny exercise?

- Strongly distrust
- Somewhat distrust
- Neutral
- Somewhat trust
- Strongly trust

Follow-up Questions (based on trust level): In the previous answer, you mentioned you feel [neutral][distrust][trust] about the accuracy of ChatGPT’s responses when working on the Dafny exercise. Why?

Overall, how helpful was ChatGPT in solving the Dafny exercise?

- I didn’t use ChatGPT for this
- Made it much harder
- Made it slightly harder
- I used ChatGPT, but it didn’t make things easier or harder
- Made it slightly easier
- Made it much easier

For each of the following, how helpful was ChatGPT? (Same scale as above)

- Understand the goal of the exercise
- Understand the code given for the exercise
- Deal with pre and post-conditions
- Find asserts that make methods verifiable
- Implement the program logic
- Write syntactically correct code
- Not mix implementation with ghost variables
- Follow exactly what the exercise is asking for
- Describe other specification constructs (modifies/reads/decreases/...)

Other tasks where you used ChatGPT's assistance (optional):

What did ChatGPT struggle with or fail to help you adequately?

If ChatGPT had been unavailable, how would that have impacted your time?

- Definitely less time
- Probably less time
- About the same
- Probably more time
- Definitely more time

No ChatGPT

Instructions:

1. Download the Exercise: [LINK](#)
2. Submit Your Code. Upload the solution below, even if incomplete.

You only have 30 minutes to submit your response.

Performance Rating:

- Very poorly
- Poorly
- Neutral
- Well
- Very well

Confidence Level:

- Not at all confident
- Slightly confident
- Moderately confident
- Very confident
- Extremely confident

If ChatGPT had been available, how would it have impacted your time?

- Definitely less time
- Probably less time
- About the same
- Probably more time
- Definitely more time

Demographic Information

How often do you use AI (e.g., ChatGPT, Claude, etc.) when working on Dafny exercises?

- Every time

- Most times
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

How often do you use AI-based tools in your IDE (e.g., GitHub Copilot)?

- Every time
- Most times
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

If you use any AI tools: **Which AI tools do you use?**

Age:

- 18-19
- 20-24
- ...
- Prefer not to say

Gender Identity:

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary / third gender
- Prefer to self-describe: _____
- Prefer not to say

Race/Ethnicity (select all that apply):

- White or Caucasian
- Black or African American
- American Indian or Alaska Native
- Asian
- Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander
- Prefer to self-describe: _____
- Prefer not to say

Highest Level of Education:

- Some high school or less
- High school diploma or GED
- Some college, but no degree
- Associates or technical degree
- Bachelor's degree
- Graduate or professional degree (e.g., MA, MS, PhD)
- Prefer not to say

1 RQ2. Codebooks

Table 1: Codebook – RQ2 analysis of the prompts. **N1** indicates the number of prompts; **N2** indicates number of users.

N1	N2	Code	Description
Prompt Characteristics			
34	12	<code>instruction</code>	User provides an instruction
23	8	<code>question</code>	User asks a question
16	12	<code>classCopy</code>	User copies the entire class in the prompt
35	13	<code>subproblemCopy</code>	User copies one or more subproblems
39	13	<code>firstSubproblem</code>	User asks about the first subproblem
54	13	<code>secondSubproblem</code>	User asks about the second subproblem
17	12	<code>hasClassInformation</code>	Class info is provided (fields and invariants)
34	13	<code>subproblemDeclaration</code>	Subproblem declaration is included
31	13	<code>subproblemSpec</code>	Subproblem specification is provided
4	3	<code>promptFrustrated</code>	User appears frustrated
2	2	<code>promptPleased</code>	User appears pleased
Retry Strategies			
9	6	<code>codeIncrementation</code>	Adds code components and asks AI to continue
4	4	<code>retry</code>	Repeats the same prompt (error not clearly specified)
5	5	<code>reduceToOneSubproblem</code>	Focuses on a single subproblem or method
6	6	<code>expandScope</code>	Adds information while preserving the original intent
8	6	<code>reduceSubproblemScope</code>	Narrows down the request inside the method
3	3	<code>reword</code>	Reformulates the prompt
8	7	<code>redirectAI</code>	Guides the AI or teaches Dafny concepts
43	12	<code>addVerificationErrors</code>	Adds error messages or types
26	12	<code>addProblematicLines</code>	Indicates lines causing verification errors
1	1	<code>chainOfThoughtsRepair</code>	Requests step-by-step or thought-driven responses
AI Response (Other Aspects)			
11	6	<code>questionAnswerCorrect</code>	AI gave a correct explanation
15	6	<code>wasQuestion</code>	The previous prompt was a question
40	10	<code>stuck</code>	AI is stuck repeating incorrect output or failed fixes
User Interaction Summary			
-	6	<code>promptingOnly</code>	User only interacted with AI until solution
-	4	<code>mostlyPrompting</code>	Mostly used AI, with minimal manual edits
-	4	<code>mostlyAutonomous</code>	Mostly implemented code independently
-	2	<code>startsWithPartial</code>	Started with partial user implementation
-	3	<code>interactionFrustrated</code>	User appears frustrated
-	1	<code>interactionPleased</code>	User appears pleased

Table 2: Codebook – RQ2 analysis of the prompts for AI code responses **N1** indicates the number of prompts; **N2** indicates number of users.

N1	N2	Code	Description
AI Response (Code-Related) SubProblem 1			
34	13	<code>Code</code>	Contains code related to the subproblem
12	3	<code>syntacticInvalid</code>	Code has syntax errors
4	2	<code>semanticInvalid</code>	Code has semantic issues (e.g., ghost variable misuse)
15	6	<code>failsGhostSeparation</code>	Ghost and implementation code are mixed
0	0	<code>correctAskedForComponent</code>	Correctly implements requested parts
13	8	<code>subproblemCorrectFunct</code>	Subproblem logic is correct regardless of spec
7	3	<code>subproblemPartialFunct</code>	Subproblem logic is partially correct
17	9	<code>correctSpecification</code>	Specification is complete and correct
11	5	<code>partialSpecification</code>	Specification is partially correct
7	7	<code>correctVerification</code>	Passes Dafny verification
6	2	<code>overlyComplex</code>	Includes unnecessary complexity (lemmas, aux vars)
12	12	<code>hasEnoughContext</code>	Prompt history has enough context
AI Response (Code-Related) SubProblem 2			
47	12	<code>code</code>	Contains code related to the subproblem
15	4	<code>syntacticInvalid</code>	Code has syntax errors
6	6	<code>semanticInvalid</code>	Code has semantic issues (e.g., ghost variable misuse)
7	3	<code>failsGhostSeparation</code>	Ghost and implementation code are mixed
1	1	<code>correctAskedForComponent</code>	Correctly implements requested parts
32	9	<code>subproblemCorrectFunct</code>	Subproblem logic is correct regardless of spec
5	3	<code>subproblemPartialFunct</code>	Subproblem logic is partially correct
22	7	<code>correctSpecification</code>	Specification is complete and correct
20	7	<code>partialSpecification</code>	Specification is partially correct
5	2	<code>correctVerification</code>	Passes Dafny verification
4	2	<code>overlyComplex</code>	Includes unnecessary complexity (lemmas, aux vars)
11	11	<code>hasEnoughContext</code>	Prompt history has enough context
AI Response (Other Aspects)			
11	6	<code>questionAnswerCorrect</code>	AI gave a correct explanation
15	6	<code>wasQuestion</code>	The previous prompt was a question
40	10	<code>stuck</code>	AI is stuck repeating incorrect output or failed fixes

2 RQ3. Trust Codebook

Table 3: Reasons for Trust and Distrust in ChatGPT

Category	Code	Description
I trust ChatGPT because...		
3	accurateCode	Correctly solved issues or gave working code.
1	usefulExplanations	Gave clear or helpful concept explanations.
2	independentCheck	Suggestions could be independently verified.
1	betterThanNothing	Trusted due to lack of personal confidence.
Distrust		
1	wrongGeneral	Seemingly plausible but incorrect solutions.
4	wrongSyntax	Frequent syntax errors or needed corrections.
1	hallucinatedFeatures	Mentioned non-existent features or capabilities.
1	notForVerification	Not suitable for verification tasks.
2	overconfidence	Repeated unhelpful answers.
1	trustExperience	Based on negative past experiences.

3 Binary Search Tree Exercise

Listing 1.1: Three Exercise

```

1  /*
2  The following code contains the implementation of a binary search tree with
3  height information among its ghost variables.
4
5  You are asked to:
6  1. Implement the method Cut, while maintaining the pre- and post-conditions
7     (you can still add other relevant specifications, like modifies, reads,
8     asserts, etc.). The goal is to make an implementation that Dafny can verify
9     against the specification;
10 2. Implement and specify the method AddAll, which should add all the provided
11   elements to the tree, and ensure all the relevant post-conditions (to be
12   added by you). Note: you can use other methods of this class to help you.
13 */
14
15 /// <summary>
16 /// Auxiliary function <c>Max</c> returns the maximum of two integers.
17 /// </summary>
18 function Max(a: int, b: int): int
19 {
20   if a > b then a else b
21 }
22
23 class BSTNode
24 {
25   // Concrete variables
26   const data: int // direct value of the node
27   var left: BSTNode? // left child
28   var right: BSTNode? // right child
29
30   // Ghost variables
31   ghost var Repr: set<object> // set of objects in the tree
32   ghost var Contents: set<int> // contents of the tree as a set
33   ghost var Height: int // height of the subtree rooted at this node
34
35   ghost predicate Valid()
36     reads this, Repr
37   {
38     // Repr contains this node
39     this in Repr &&
40     // BST properties:
41     // - all elements in the left subtree are less than the node's data
42     // - all elements in the right subtree are greater than the node's data
43     // - the left and right subtrees are valid BSTs
44     // - the Repr set is consistent
45     (left != null ==>
46       left in Repr &&
47       left.Repr <= Repr && this !in left.Repr &&
48       (forall e :: e in left.Contents ==> e < data) &&
49       left.Valid()) &&
50     (right != null ==>
51       right in Repr &&
52       right.Repr <= Repr && this !in right.Repr &&
53       (forall e :: e in right.Contents ==> data < e) &&
54       right.Valid())
55     // Left and right subtrees do not overlap

```

```

56  && (left != null && right != null ==> left.Repr !! right.Repr)
57  // The contents of the tree do not overlap
58  && (left != null ==> data !in left.Contents)
59  && (right != null ==> data !in right.Contents)
60  && (left != null && right != null ==> left.Contents !! right.Contents)
61  // Contents is the union of the contents of the left and right subtrees plus the node's data
62  && Contents == (if left == null then {} else left.Contents) +
63                 (if right == null then {} else right.Contents) +
64                 {data}
65  // Height is correctly defined
66  && Height == Max(if left == null then 0 else left.Height,
67                  if right == null then 0 else right.Height)
68                  + 1
69  }
70
71  constructor (x: int)
72    ensures fresh(Repr - {this})
73    ensures Valid()
74    ensures Contents == {x}
75  {
76    data := x;
77    left := null;
78    right := null;
79    Repr := { this };
80    Contents := { data };
81    Height := 1;
82  }
83
84  /// <summary>
85  /// Method <c>Insert</c> adds an element to the tree, if not already
86  /// present, while maintaining the binary search tree properties.
87  /// </summary>
88  method Insert(x: int)
89    requires Valid()
90    modifies Repr
91    decreases Repr
92    ensures Valid()
93    ensures fresh(Repr - old(Repr))
94    ensures Contents == old(Contents) + {x}
95    ensures Height == old(Height) || Height == old(Height) + 1
96  {
97    if x == data { return; }
98    if x < data {
99      if left == null {
100         left := new BSTNode(x);
101       } else {
102         left.Insert(x);
103       }
104       Height := Max(left.Height, if right == null then 0 else right.Height) + 1;
105       Repr := Repr + left.Repr;
106     } else {
107       if right == null {
108         right := new BSTNode(x);
109       } else {
110         right.Insert(x);
111       }
112       Height := Max(if left == null then 0 else left.Height, right.Height) + 1;
113       Repr := Repr + right.Repr;
114     }

```

```

115     Contents := Contents + {x};
116 }
117
118 /// <summary>
119 /// Method <c>Cut</c> should "cut" the tree at the provided height,
120 /// discarding all descendants with depth higher than that.
121 /// </summary>
122 method Cut(height : int)
123     requires height > 0
124     requires Valid()
125     ensures Valid()
126     ensures fresh(Repr - old(Repr))
127     ensures Height <= height
128     ensures Contents <= old(Contents)
129 {
130     // TODO: Implement this method (Exercise 1)
131 }
132
133 /// <summary>
134 /// Method <c>AddAll</c> adds all elements of a sequence to the tree.
135 /// </summary>
136 method AddAll(other: seq<int>)
137     // TODO: Specify this method (Exercise 2)
138 {
139     // TODO: Implement this method (Exercise 2)
140 }
141 }

```

4 Circular Buffer Queue Exercise

Listing 1.2: Queue Exercise

```

1 /*
2 The following code contains the implementation of a queue using a circular
3 buffer using variables to keep track of the queue's position.
4
5 You are asked to:
6 1. Implement the method Dequeue, while maintaining the pre- and post-conditions
7 (you can still add other relevant specifications, like modifies, reads,
8 asserts, etc.). The goal is to make an implementation that Dafny can verify
9 against the specification;
10 2. Implement and specify the method Queue, which should add an element to the
11 end of the queue and ensure all the relevant post-conditions (to be added by
12 you).
13 */
14 class CircularBuffer<T>
15 {
16     // Concrete variables
17     const buffer: array<T> // buffer
18     var used_size: nat // size of the queue
19     var head: nat // position of the queue's head
20
21     // Ghost variables
22     ghost const capacity: nat // capacity of the buffer
23     ghost var tail: nat // position of the queue's tail
24     ghost var contents: seq<T> // contents of the queue
25

```

```

26 ghost predicate Valid()
27   reads this, buffer
28 {
29   // The buffer's capacity must be greater than 0
30   capacity > 0 &&
31   // The head must be a valid position in the buffer
32   0 <= head < capacity &&
33   // The size of the queue must be between 0 and the buffer's capacity
34   0 <= used_size <= capacity &&
35   // The buffer's length must be equal to the capacity
36   capacity == buffer.Length &&
37   // The size of the queue must be equal to the length of the contents
38   used_size == |contents| &&
39   // The tail is calculated like follows:
40   // In case the buffer happens to be like [A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, I, J]
41   //
42   //
43   //           head
44   // The tail is simply adding the size to the head in case it's still in the
45   // buffer, like for size 5: [A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, I, J]
46   //
47   //           head           tail
48   // In case the tail is outside the buffer, we need to subtract the capacity
49   // from the tail, like for size 8: [A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, I, J]
50   //
51   //           tail head
52   tail == (if head + used_size < capacity
53           then head + used_size
54           else head + used_size - capacity) &&
55   // The contents of the queue are equal to the elements in the buffer
56   // between the head and the tail, being sure to wrap around the buffer
57   // in case the tail is less than the head
58   contents == if used_size == 0
59   then []
60   else if tail > head
61   then buffer[head..tail]
62   else buffer[head..capacity] + buffer[0..tail]
63 }
64
65 constructor (capacity: nat, instantiator: int -> T)
66   requires capacity > 0
67   ensures Valid()
68   ensures fresh(buffer)
69 {
70   this.capacity := capacity;
71   buffer := new T[capacity](instantiator);
72   head := 0;
73   used_size := 0;
74   tail := 0;
75   contents := [];
76 }
77
78 /// <summary>
79 /// Method <c>Dequeue</c> pops the first element of the queue and returns it.
80 /// Note that the value is the first element of the queue, which means the
81 /// return is 'contents[0]'.
82 /// </summary>
83 method Dequeue() returns (elem: T)
84   requires Valid()
85   requires used_size > 0

```

```
85     ensures elem == old(contents[0])
86     ensures contents == old(contents[1..])
87     ensures Valid()
88     {
89         // TODO: Implement this method (Exercise 1)
90     }
91
92     /// <summary>
93     /// Method <c>Queue</c> takes an element and adds it to the end of the queue.
94     /// Note that it should be added to the end of the queue, abstractly
95     /// represented by the sequence 'contents'.
96     /// </summary>
97     method Queue(elem: T)
98         // TODO: Specify this method (Exercise 2)
99     {
100         // TODO: Implement this method (Exercise 2)
101     }
102 }
```